

THE IMPACT OF HOUSEHOLD FINANCE

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***Abstract:** Household financial decisions are complex, interdependent, and heterogeneous, and central to the functioning of the financial system. We present an overview of the rapidly expanding literature on household finance (with some important exceptions) and suggest directions for future research. We begin with the theory and empirics of asset market participation and asset allocation over the life cycle. We then discuss household choices in insurance markets, trading behavior, decisions on retirement saving, and financial choices by retirees. We survey research on liabilities, including mortgage choice, refinancing, and default, and household behavior in unsecured credit markets, including credit cards and payday lending. We then connect the household to its social environment, including peer effects, cultural and hereditary factors, intra-household financial decision-making, financial literacy, cognition, and educational interventions. We also discuss literature on the provision and consumption of financial advice.*

***Keywords:** household finance, saving, consumption, investment, housing, borrowing, fintech.*

Introduction:

Household finance plays a crucial role in shaping consumer spending patterns and contributing to overall economic growth. Efficient management of household finances is essential for maintaining financial stability, achieving individual economic well-being, and fostering macroeconomic stability. This thesis aims to explore the various aspects of household finance and analyze its implications for consumer spending and economic growth.

Definition of Consumer Finance

Household finance is the field of financial economics that studies how households use financial instruments and markets to achieve their objectives. Normative household finance studies how households should take financial decisions by building models of optimal portfolio choice and financing decision over the lifecycle. Positive household finance investigates empirically what households actually do with their money and how they do borrow.

Consumer finance was first used in 1983 when the Survey of Consumer Finance started. In 2008, an edited book contributed by economists, business researchers, and consumer scientists, used consumer finance in its title. Later, Peter Tufano published an overview article that summarized the consumer finance research. Based on these scholars' backgrounds, they proposed these terms from different perspectives. Campbell is an economist and he viewed this topic from a public perspective. Tufano is a finance professor in business school and proposed this topic from a business perspective. Xiao is a consumer science professor and viewed this topic from a consumer perspective. Other terms are variations of these two terms. For example, behavioral finance is a variation of behavioral economics that focuses on basic research on human behaviors. Many studies on behavioral finance are about individual and family behaviors. Family finance and personal finance are variations of consumer finance from researchers in consumer science, which emphasize financial issues faced by families and individuals. In terms of research purposes, economists are interested in the social welfare that includes multiple interest groups such as businesses, consumers, governments, and other social organizations. Business school researchers

are concerned about the interest of shareholders of businesses. Consumer science researchers are interested in the wellbeing of consumers that include individuals and families.

There are several factors that can influence household financial decisions. These include:

- Income
- Expenses.
- Debt
- Financial goals
- Risk tolerance
- Economic conditions
- Age and life stage
- Financial literacy
- Cultural and societal influences
- Personal factors

Household finance plays a crucial role in personal financial management for several reasons:

1. Budgeting: Household finance helps individuals and families to create and maintain a budget. A budget is a financial plan that outlines income and expenses and helps individuals track their spending habits. By managing household finances, individuals can identify areas where they can cut back on expenses and allocate funds towards important goals such as saving for retirement or paying off debt.

2. Financial Stability: Proper management of household finance ensures financial stability for individuals and families. This includes saving for emergencies, paying bills on time, and avoiding unnecessary debt. By being financially stable, individuals can minimize financial stress and have a better overall quality of life.

3. Debt Management: Proper household finance management enables individuals to manage and reduce their debt effectively. By understanding their financial situation and creating a debt payoff plan, individuals can prioritize their debt payments and work towards becoming debt-free.

4. Goal Setting: Household finance allows individuals to set and achieve their financial goals. Whether it's buying a house, saving for education, or planning for retirement, understanding and managing household finances is essential for setting realistic goals and taking the necessary steps to achieve them.

5. Financial Education: Managing household finances provides individuals with the opportunity to educate themselves about personal finance. By learning about various financial concepts such as investing, insurance, and taxes, individuals can make informed decisions and take control of their financial future.

6. Improved Decision Making: By managing household finances, individuals can make better financial decisions. They can prioritize their spending, differentiate between needs and wants, and make long-term financial plans. This leads to better financial outcomes and a more secure financial future..

Table 1

Description of the main indicators determining the economy of the region

t/r	Indicators	Brief description and object of study
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1	Lifestyle and society	The level of literacy of the population of the region, the state of cultural and educational institutions in the region, and the spiritual image of the population of the region
2	Demographic processes	The weight of nationalities and peoples in the region, the birth and death rates in the region, the state of labor migration in the region, and the measures being taken to eliminate demographic problems in the region
3	Foreign economic and trade relations	Mutual economic and trade relations of the region with other regions within the country and foreign countries; export and import possibilities of the region
4	Territorial management	The structure of the regional administration, the state of making administrative decisions regarding the regional economy, and the level of support for the attraction of investments at the level of the regional administration
5	Science and technology	The state of activity of science and technology development centers in the region and the state of acceptance and implementation of science and technology development programs in the region
6	Infrastructures in the area	The state of transport and logistics communication, the state of supply of electricity, natural gas, and water resources for production in the area
7	Natural resources	All natural resources in the area and the level of their use
8	Economic indicators of the region	Economic indicators of the region's development, its financial and credit system, and opportunities for doing business in the region

Although the last of the eight indicators listed in the table refers to economic indicators, the highlighted parameters are recommended for entrepreneurs interested in investing in a specific area. However, it is acceptable to study not only economic development indicators but also other parameters related to these factors in a complex way. The mutual relations between production forces and regions are taken into account in the placement of production forces. High efficiency of production and the volume of income should be given great importance in the rational placement of production forces in economic development.

The relationship between household income and spending patterns is complex and can vary depending on individual circumstances and economic factors. However, some general trends can be observed:

Disposable income: Higher household income generally leads to increased disposable income, which is the amount of money available for spending and saving after essential expenses such as taxes and bills are deducted. This can result in higher spending on discretionary items and non-essential goods and services.

Basic needs: While higher-income households may have more money available for spending, they may also have higher expenses related to basic needs such as housing, healthcare, and education. These expenses can limit the amount of discretionary income available for other categories of spending.

Lifestyle inflation: As household income increases, there may be a tendency for spending to increase as well. This phenomenon, known as lifestyle inflation, occurs when individuals or families increase their spending to match or exceed their higher income levels. It can lead to higher spending on luxury items, travel, dining out, and other discretionary purchases.

Savings and investments: Higher-income households may have more capacity to save and invest compared to lower-income households. They may allocate a larger proportion of their income towards savings, retirement accounts, and investments. Saving patterns can vary based on individual financial goals and risk tolerance.

Debt and credit usage: Higher-income households may have better access to credit and may be more likely to accumulate debt, such as mortgages, car loans, and credit card debt. However, they may also be better positioned to manage and pay off debt due to their higher income levels.

Economic conditions: Spending patterns can be influenced by broader economic conditions, such as inflation rates, interest rates, and general consumer confidence. During periods of economic growth and stability, households may be more inclined to increase their spending and make larger purchases. Conversely, during economic downturns or recessions, households may reduce their spending and prioritize saving or paying off debt.

It's essential to note that these trends are not absolute and can vary significantly depending on individual financial goals, personal circumstances, and cultural factors. Additionally, these relationships can change over time due to shifts in economic conditions and individual income fluctuations.

Figure 2. Absorption of foreign direct investments and loans within the framework of regional investment projects, in millions of US dollars

Based on the regional investment project, according to the monetary expression of foreign investments made in the first quarter of 2022 and 2023, Tashkent city (347.5 and 1238.5 million US dollars), Tashkent region (195.8 and 482.4 million US dollars) and Samarkand the amount of

investment made in the region (95.3 and 514.2 million US dollars) is higher compared to other regions shown in Figure 2.

The reason why these regions have achieved a high rate in recent years is because of our president, Sh. It is the result of Mirziyoyev's attention to the development of regional entrepreneurship and small business in the regions. President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. Mirziyoyev's decision No. PQ-39 of January 31, 2023, "On additional measures to take the support of the population's business initiatives to a new level within the family entrepreneurship development programs" provides financial support for the population's entrepreneurial initiatives. Support, first of all, has set several priority goals to further improve the environment of small business and entrepreneurship in the neighborhoods and to systematically continue the activities of employment of young people and women with profitable work.

The reason why the volume of foreign investments made to regions located in the Fergana region is second only to Tashkent is that direct foreign investments and loans made to the non-state sector in this region amount to 1,168.4 billion soums, and this volume makes up 98.7% of foreign investments and loans included in the total fixed capital. The utilization of a significant part of foreign investments and loans by types of economic activities corresponds to the processing industry (906.7 billion). Its share in the volume of foreign investments and loans is 76.6%, and in the field of healthcare and social services, it is 9.1 billion soums, 0.8% of total foreign investments and loans, and wholesale and retail trade, repair of motor vehicles, and motorcycles amounted to 46.1 billion soums, 3.9% of total foreign investments and loans, and 11.2 billion for living and dining services. Soums (0.9%), information and communication (19.3 billion), Soums (1.6%), forestry, and fisheries (106.2 billion) amounted to soums (9.0%). It was observed that the absorption of foreign investments and loans in these types of economic activity increased compared to January–March 2023.

In January-March of this year, Andijan invested 428.5 million, Bukhara 317.1 million, Namangan 379 million, Navoi 246.2 million, Jizzakh 399.2 million, Khorezm 190.2 million, Syrdarya 285.3 million, and Surkhandarya 250 million. Foreign investments and loans in the amount of 2 million US dollars have been absorbed.

Foreign investment in the amount of 40.5 million US dollars was made in the Republic of Karakalpakstan. Investments and borrowed loans are considered related to the construction sector, and due to the fact that the geographical location is in a desert zone and an ecologically weak area, the volume of investments is relatively small compared to other regions of the country.

Despite the special emphasis on this field today, there are still problems and shortcomings. For this reason, based on the research carried out, our proposals that help the development of the regional economy are listed below, including:

- **Infrastructural development:** quality infrastructure, convenient, energy-saving transport infrastructure, water supply, etc. are important features for economic development. Also, organization of investments and loans in infrastructural areas.
- **Education and innovation:** Increasing knowledge in the fields of education and innovation will develop the regional economy. It is important to further develop the education system, create the necessary conditions for technical and professional training, encourage scientific research, and create innovative areas. This indicates that new ideas and technologies will be created by young people in the future.
- **Encouraging entrepreneurship:** creating favorable conditions for entrepreneurship, creating an investment environment, and ensuring the soundness and transparency of the tax

system will help promote positive changes in the industry. The increase in the volume of goods produced in industrial sectors serves to increase the GDP and ensure the economic development of the regions.

- Development of international cooperation: International cooperation is important in the development of the regional economy. Provides access to international markets and increases export potential; actively attracts foreign investments; and helps increase the likelihood of working with external sources of finance and technologies.

- Development of local industries: effective and sustainable formation of available resources in each region, stimulation of local entrepreneurship This will improve the socio-economic condition of the population.

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